

Volcanic risk communication through community stories transmitted by radio

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Supporting Information

Supplementary Methods and Results

Demographic characteristics of the population surveyed. The responses for each department were: department of Caldas 25.99%, Tolima 38.28%, Cauca 11.60%, and Nariño 24.13%. The proportions according to sex were: women (44.3%) and men (54.8%). The age distribution of the respondents was: 16–24 years (19.5 %), 25–34 years (15.8 %), 35–44 years (20.4 %), 45–54 years (21.6%), 55–64 (15.8%), and older than 64 years (5.1 %). Regarding the educational level, the percentage of respondents were: incomplete high school education level (19.95 %), a university education level (12.53 %), complete and technical postgraduate (10.9 %), and incomplete elementary (10.9%).

Table S1. Questions surveyed in the questionnaire following the four dimensions of the Antigua Manual: attitudes and values, social appropriation of knowledge and technology, institutional issues, and informational and cultural habits. Eight additional questions are related to the demographic attributes of each respondent (not shown). The interview determines the level of knowledge, processes, and strategies for communicating information on adaptation, mitigation, and response to volcanic hazard emergencies.

Antigua Manual Dimension	Question	Scale
Attitudes and values	Do you live near a volcano?	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	Do you consider that the volcano is a danger to your life, community, and property?	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	In the last five years in your municipality, has there been any risk associated with the volcanic hazard?	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	Which words or phrases do you think of when talking about risk from a volcanic hazard?	Open-ended
	How much do you consider that the volcanic hazard affects the following features in your place of residence: a. Health b. Infrastructure (bridges, buildings, parks, hospitals, and schools) c. Your living place d. Your work activities such as livestock or your crops e. Other, which one?	It affects a lot, affects a little, does not affect, does not know
Social appropriation of knowledge	Do you consider that your municipality is prepared to face the volcano's risk and/or hazard in the area?. Why?	Yes, no, don't know, or don't answer. Open-ended
	Do you know informative content that communicates emergency plans in the event of a volcanic eruption?. Which one?	Yes, no, don't know, or don't answer. Open-ended
	Have you participated in a volcanic hazard simulation?	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	Do you know which routes you should take in the event of an evacuation order	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer. Open-ended

	due to a volcanic hazard?., Which one?	
	If you answered Yes to the previous question, please indicate how it was reported.	Open-ended
	Do you know what to do in the event of a volcanic eruption?	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	If you have adopted preventive measures in the event of a volcanic emergency, indicate which ones?	Open-ended
	Have you been part of any space for citizen participation for issues related to volcanic risk in the last year? Which one?	Yes, no, don't know, or don't answer. Open-ended
	In the event of a volcano emergency, what actions/practices would you implement to deal with the situation?	Open-ended
Institutional issues	If you answered Yes to the previous question, indicate which media, people, or entities you can or should go to in case of an emergency due to volcanic activity	Open-ended
	Do you know the people or entities you can or should go to in case of an emergency due to the volcano's activity?	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	Regarding volcanic risk, you:	Yes, no, don't know or don't answer
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Have you processed complaints, claims, or requests with the corresponding authorities? b. Have you used the media such as television, radio, press, or the internet (national, local) to make a complaint or present a proposal? c. Have you requested help from any civic leader or political leader? d. Have you participated in protests and/or public marches? e. Have you developed projects or activities with members of your community? 	
Informational and cultural habits	How informed do you feel about volcanic risk?	5 point Likert scale, 1 = very informed, 2 = informed, 3 = poorly informed, 4 = not at all informed, 5 = don't know or don't answer

Through which communication media and/or mobile devices have you obtained information on volcanic risk?

1. Tv
2. Radio
3. Newspapers
4. Magazines
5. Internet
6. Mobile phone (calls and SMS)
7. Other. Which one?

Can you name a TV or radio program/newspaper/ magazine/website that you consult/seek to find out about risk and/or volcanic hazards?

Open-ended

Do you consider that the information on volcanic risk in your municipality is enough? Why?

Yes, no, don't know, or don't answer. Open-ended

What kind of information do you think should be communicated?

Open-ended

Table S2. Semi-structured interviews for officials of public entities with the role of disaster risk management of the municipalities and departments involved.

Focus group	Question
Majors and governors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name the volcanoes that you consider a hazard in your department and/or municipality. • How is Law 1523 of 2012 related to the National Disaster Risk Policy applied in the municipality from the perspective of the volcanic hazards? • What instruments and/or mechanisms related to volcanic risk have been applied or will be applied in the department and/or municipality? • Who is responsible for both the planning and the dissemination of volcanic risk information? • What is the relationship of the department or municipality with the National Unit or Disaster Risk Management (UNGRD) and the Colombian Geological Service (SGC)? • How does the government and/or municipality integrate with the National Unit for Disaster Risk Management and the Colombian Geological Service to manage risk issues due to volcanic hazards? • Who and what entities participate in the design, development, and evaluation of communication strategies? • Explain that it is not an alert, how it has been reported that there is a volcanic risk. • Which communication strategy has been most effective for the inhabitants of your municipality to manage the risk due to volcanic hazards? • Do you know, or can you account for the impact of communication strategies in the department and/or municipality? • How could the response capacity to a situation of volcanic risk be improved? • Do you know if educational campaigns have been carried out on volcanic risk? Do you remember what they are? • According to the answer to the previous question, is there an educational campaign planned for this year? • Do you consider that your department and/or municipality is prepared to face a volcanic hazard emergency?

Officials or
leaders with the
role of disaster
risk
management

- Name the volcanoes you consider a hazard to your department and/or municipality.
 - How is Law 1523 of 2012 related to the National Disaster Risk Policy applied in the municipality from the perspective of the volcanic hazards?
 - What is the relationship of the department or municipality with the National Unit for Disaster Risk Management (UNGRD) and Disaster Risk (UNGRD) and the Colombian Geological Service (SGC)? Colombian Geological Service (SGC)?
 - How do the government and/or municipality integrate with the National Unit for Disaster Risk Management and the Colombian Geological Service to communicate volcanic risk?
 - What elements of the National Plan for disaster risk management have been applied in the municipality from a volcanic hazard perspective.
 - Since you have been in your position, how have communication strategies been worked together to confront volcanic risk?
 - Do you think these strategies have been effective? Why?
 - What recommendations would you give for a communication strategy on volcanic risk to be effective?
 - What topics do you think should be disclosed in a communication strategy on volcanic risk?
 - What are the key actors that must be taken into account to create and promote a communication strategy on volcanic risk?
 - What non-formal participation mechanisms have they generated or built to design, implement and evaluate communication or participation strategies related to volcanic risk?
 - Are you aware of communication initiatives developed by the communities related to the risk of volcanic hazards?
 - Have communication strategies been designed and implemented in co-production with communities in areas of volcanic hazards? Which ones?
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Table S3. List of officials of public entities with the role of disaster risk management of the municipalities and departments involved in the semi-structured interviews.

- Guillermo Avila. (2016) Professional Red Cross of the municipality of Venadillo, Tolima.
- Ana María Calapsú. (2016). Governor of the Indigenous Reservation of Puracé, Nariño.
- Daniel Cano. (2016). Director of the National Unit for Risk and Disaster Management of Manizales, Caldas.
- Guido Echeverri. (2016). Governor of Caldas, Caldas.
- Felix Giraldo. (2016). Coordinator, Departmental Unit for Disaster Risk Management of Caldas, Manizales.
- Juan Alejandro Holguín. (2016). Mayor of the municipality of Villamaría, Caldas.
- Germán Jaramillo. (2016). Commander of the Fire Department of the municipality of Palestina, Caldas.
- Second Malte. (2016). Governor of the Indigenous Reserve of Chiles, Nariño.
- Olmedo Quilindo. (2016). President of the Manuel María Mosquera School, Puracé Indigenous Reserve, Cauca.
- Rubielo Quintero. (2016). Fire Lieutenant of the municipality of Villamaría, Caldas.
- Alex Velasquez. (2016). School teacher Londoño Jaramillo, Río Claro, Caldas.

Figure S1. Communicative and educational resources of the Volcano, Risk and Territory strategy of Colombia. These resources on volcanic risk reduction (a) include a web page (b), participatory volcanic hazard maps (c), a virtual learning space (d), manuals for community leaders (e), and videos (f). Please see further details of this strategy at UNGRD (2021).

Figure S2. Examples of social cartography carried out with the key social actors. Officials of public entities map of Guayabal, Tolima (A) and Chiles, Nariño (B). Local community map of Río Claro, Caldas (C). School teachers' map of Cumbal, Nariño (D). Social cartography is a qualitative methodology to identify the economic and social relations of the communities in a territory through cartographic language that materializes iconographic discourses. Some examples of these relationships are boundaries, land use, conflicts, history, or solidarity. Regarding volcanic hazards, social cartography is used to observe how communities imagine and understand the volcano and know the areas they consider to be of high risk and their possible effects on the territory. Also, to establish how the participants imagine the specific location of the actors with technical or professional functions linked to disaster risk management. The cartographic exercises are a participatory construction without the expectation of technical accuracy in terms of scales and proportions of spaces (Velez Torres, et al, 2012)

Bibliography

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